

Magnetic Susceptibilities of Some Inorganic and Organic Electronic Isomers.

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In a recent paper Bhatnagar and Dhawan (*Phil. Mag.*, 1928, 5, 536) have discussed the following equation : -

$$\chi_m = -2.85 \times 10^{10} \times (Kr_1)^2 \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where χ_m is the molecular susceptibility, r_1 the mean radius of the molecule calculated from W. L. Bragg's data in a manner described before (*loc. cit.*) and K is an arbitrary constant. This equation has been shown to hold for a large number of electronic isomers. In order to understand the full significance of the constant K and to bring the above equation into line with the original Langevin equation, Bhatnagar and Mathur put this equation into a modified form in a subsequent publication (*Phil. Mag.*, 1928, 6, 217). Due to an unfortunate misprint in the first paper the original equation of Langevin in the second paper has been unnecessarily multiplied by $\frac{2}{3}$ and the equation modified by us, when correction is made for this, should read as -

$$\chi_m = -2.85 \times 10^{10} \times k (r_1)^2 \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

This equation differs from equation (1) only by the fact that k has been brought out of the brackets from equation (1) and as such k is equal to K^2 .

In this paper further experimental evidence has been brought forward in support of equation (2). That value of the constant has been adopted which gives the best possible results with all members in a particular set of electronic isomers. This is justified as the experimental values of susceptibilities are perhaps more or less equally accurate in all cases.

The method employed for the determination of susceptibilities is the one described by Oxley and Wilson and used in our previous papers (*loc. cit.*).

Special precautions were taken to purify the substances chemically as well as magnetically. The accuracy of the magnetic balance is within approximately $\pm 10\%$. In Table I are given the values of

susceptibilities and the calculated radii of the molecules from Bragg's data of atomic diameters. The last column shows the susceptibilities as they will come out on calculation by employing the numbers of k and r_1 , in equation (2).

TABLE I.

<i>A. Electronic Isomers (Inorganic).</i>					
Atomic number.	Names.	Mean values of k calculated from equation (2).	Values of r_1 in Å calc. from Bragg's data.	$-\chi_m \times 10^6$ Experimental.	$-\chi_m \times 10^6$ Calculated from the mean value of k .
46	NaBr	1.3	2.965	30.77	32.56
46	SrO	1.3	2.60	28.02	25.04
78	AgNO ₃	4.0	1.885	41.19	40.53
78	CdCO ₃	4.0	1.752	36.02	34.98
<i>B. Electronic Isomers (Organic).</i>					
72	Aminobenzoic acid* NH ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .CO ₂ H	10.34	1.717	85.8	86.84
72	Nitrotoluene* CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ .NO ₂	10.34	1.717	87.9	86.84
56	Valeric acid* C ₄ H ₉ .CO ₂ H	8.0	1.629	61.09	60.64
56	Propyl acetate* CH ₃ .CO.O.C ₃ H ₇	8.0	1.629	60.1	60.64
96	Benzophenone. (C ₆ H ₅) ₂ CO	11.26	1.974	119.9	125.0
96	Galactose. C ₆ H ₁₂ O ₆	11.26	1.834	113.7	107.9
76	Isatin. C ₈ H ₅ O ₂ N	9.0	1.735	81.04	77.16
76	Phthalimide. C ₈ H ₅ (CO) ₂ NH	9.0	1.735	86.06	77.16
66	Ethylaniline. C ₈ H ₉ NHC ₂ H ₅	9.74	1.772	87.14	87.18
66	Dimethylaniline. C ₈ H ₉ .N(CH ₃) ₂	9.74	1.772	79.34	87.18
66	Collidine. C ₈ H ₉ .N(CH ₃) ₃	9.74	1.772	83.18	87.18

Before discussing the results it would be interesting to give the values of k for previously described electronic isomers (Bhatnagar and Dhawan; *Phil. Mag.*, 1928, 5, 536) and Bhatnagar and Mathur (*Phil. Mag.*, 1928, 6, 217) as calculated on equation (2) in this paper.

TABLE II.

A. *Electronic Isomers (Inorganic).*

Atomic number.	Names.	Mean values of k calculated from equation (2).	Values of τ_1 in Å calc. from Bragg's data.	$-\chi_m \times 10^6$ Experimental.	$-\chi_m \times 10^6$ calculated from the mean value of k .
28	NaCl*	1	2.825	23.96	22.74
28	CaO*	1	2.35	15.14	15.74
72	CaCl*	1.42	3.425	47.13	47.45
72	KI	1.42	3.475	51.46	48.85
78	TeH ₂ O ₃ *	5.5	1.515	33.73	35.97
78	ZnSO ₄ *	5.5	1.646	43.58	42.46

B. *Electronic Isomers (Organic).*

48	Butyric acid. CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₂ CO ₂ H	8.69	1.528	60	57.79
48	Ethylacetate. CH ₃ CO.OCC ₂ H ₅	8.69	1.528	55	57.79
40	Methylacetate. CH ₃ COOCH ₃	6.59	1.411	35.89	37.39
40	Propionic acid. CH ₃ CH ₂ CO ₂ H	6.59	1.411	38.92	37.39
58	Anisole.* C ₆ H ₅ OCH ₃	8.2	1.67	64.98	65.16
58	Benzyl alcohol.* C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ OH	8.2	1.67	65.58	65.16
58	Phenyl hydrazine.* C ₆ H ₅ NHNH ₂	8.2	1.648	62.03	63.46
58	<i>o</i> -Cresol.* CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ .OH	8.2	1.67	65.16	65.16
58	Toluidine. CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ .NH ₂	9.40	1.689	76.37	76.43
58	Methylaniline. C ₆ H ₅ .NHCH ₃	9.40	1.689	76.61	76.43
40	<i>iso</i> -Butyl aldehyde (CH ₃) ₂ CHCHO	7.54	1.488	47.45	47.6
40	Methyl ethyl ketone. CH ₃ COC ₂ H ₅	7.54	1.488	47.74	47.6
72	Methyl benzoate. C ₆ H ₅ COOCH ₃	9.46	1.754	89.23	82.92
72	Phenyl acetate. CH ₃ COOC ₆ H ₅	9.46	1.754	82.69	89.92
50	Glycerine* CH ₂ OH.CHOH.CH ₂ OH	8.96	1.502	56.82	57.61
50	Aniline* C ₆ H ₅ .NH ₂	8.96	1.595	65.17	64.97

* For these substances the values of $-\chi_m \times 10^6$ have been taken from the "Physico-chemical Tables" of Landolt and Börnstein. Most of the remaining values have been determined experimentally by Messrs. C. L. Dabwan and S. L. Luther. The values of τ_1 have been recalculated on the basis of atomic radius of H = 0.53 Å.

Discussion of Results.

A close examination of the above table shows three significant relations between the values of k .

(a) The values of k tend to increase with the number of atoms contained in the molecule. For example, in the case of molecules having five atoms the value of k is 4. For molecules having 13 atoms it is as great as 7.54 and for those having 24 atoms it is 11.26. In the case of substances marked by (*) the values of k are slightly out of this rule but still the trend is, in general, in the same direction.

(b) In the case of groups of isomers having the same number of atoms in the molecule, the values of k increase with the atomic numbers of the groups. For example (NaCl and CaO) and (CsCl and KI) are two groups of electronic isomers having the same number of atoms in the molecule, but having different atomic numbers 28 and 72 respectively. And the value of k in the latter group is greater than that in the former. Similar relations also exist between the groups of electronic isomers having 14, 16, and 17 atoms in the molecule.

(c) In the case of groups of electronic isomers having the same atomic number, the values of k increase with the number of atoms as shown in the table below.

TABLE III.

Atomic number.	No. of atoms.	Substance.	Values of k .
<i>Inorganic isomers.</i>			
78	5	AgNO ₃	4.0
78	5	CdCO ₃	4.0
78	6	TeH ₂ O ₃	5.5
78	6	ZnSO ₄	5.5
<i>Organic isomers.</i>			
40	11	Methyl acetate.	6.59
40	11	Propionic acid.	6.59
40	13	isoButyl aldehyde.	7.54
40	13	Methyl ethyl ketone.	7.54

Similar relations also exist when the atomic number is 58. A slight discrepancy is observed in the values of k for aminobenzoic acid and nitrotoluene.

The above significant facts about the constant k suggest that equation (2) may be of fundamental physical significance. It is clear from (a), (c) and (d) that the value of k is a function of both the number of atoms in the molecule and its atomic number—an observation that is easily intelligible on the modern concept of diamagnetism.

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